

DIGITAL FLAT PANEL COCKPIT DISPLAYS AND SPECIFICATION*

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ABSTRACT

Flight instrument design has begun to include a new, digital electronic technology for the display head: active matrix liquid crystal display (AMLCD). This is a significant design transition and applies across the board to new systems, complete cockpit modernization programs, and individual instrument replacement projects. AMLCD-based instruments are digital and are expected to have a substantially higher mean time between failure compared to both electromechanical and CRT-based instruments, which are typically analog. Thus, the new technology will pay for itself. Furthermore, AMLCDs are truly sunlight-readable and can provide large display areas enabling formats which increase situational awareness. We have the opportunity with this new technology to establish a common critical item products for sunlight-readable, color and greyscale capable, flat panel displays for military applications.

INTRODUCTION

An epochal change in flight instrument technology has begun. Electromechanical and cathode ray tube (CRT) displays are being superseded by flat panel cockpit displays (FPCDs) in all classes of flight instrument: military aviation, commercial aviation, general aviation, and space vehicles. A similar transition is approaching for other applications having similar requirements, such as field laptop computers, field communication suitcases, and automotive cockpits. This transformation will accelerate during the mid-1990s. The basis for this epochal change is illustrated in Figure 1: active matrix liquid crystal displays (AMLCDs) have significantly increased the display capability realized in fielded applications in several key regards, including performance, life-cycle costs, display size, weight, and

Figure 1. Capability of flight instruments with time and display technology. Arrival of AMLCD provides impetus for epochal shift.

power. It is no longer necessary, for example, to accept displays that are not full color, can not be read in full sunlight, are not affordable.

DIGITAL FLAT PANEL COCKPIT DISPLAYS

The Cockpit Avionics Office initiated the establishment of a functional specification for FPCDs and a standard for AMLCDs for militarized flight instruments in April 1992. No such common specification or standard exists and it is absolutely necessary that they be developed prior to the impending revolution in fielded electronic displays. Furthermore, the standard will permit us to capitalize on the opportunity to establish common display modules for use in several platforms across services. The specification and standard are to be as common as practicable with other military and commercial uses. All concerned government and industry entities are welcome

to participate in this process which may take two additional years to complete. The first phase was completed April 1993 and comprised (1) formulation of a Working Draft Specification, (2) solicitation of written comments, and (3) a workshop [1]. The first phase had as its objective the identification and involvement of stakeholders in government and industry. The second phase will involve several smaller workshops and has the objectives of the Draft FPCD Specification and the AMLCD Standard, both for digital flight instrument display heads (FIDH), by the end of calendar 1993. The third phase will involve publication of the Specification and Standard next year. Requirements and industrial base considerations have been presented elsewhere [2].

This functional specification can only be met at present by AMLCDs. Thus, the first standard is specifically for AMLCD display head modules. A general, or guide, specification for electronically and optically generated airborne displays, independent of any particular technology, has recently been published [3]. Standards for other flat panel display technologies will be prepared separately as needed. Many such technologies are in research and development for cockpit applications, as detailed by Hopper [4] and Runyon [5].

The design baseline for flight instruments comprises a-Si TFT on glass substrate with chip-on-flex 16-graylevel drivers and a backlight system using fluorescent tubes coupled with dimming circuitry (685 cd m^{-2} upper limit for day, down to a lower limit of 0.10 cd m^{-2} for night) and 10:1 contrast. The preferred pixel shape is square (RGBG quad-square subpixel elements for color) with addressable element density of about 6.3 mm^{-1} (160 in^{-1}) in direct view and 38.8 mm^{-1} (985 in^{-1}) in helmet/head mounted. The design goal is at least one pixel every 100 arcseconds (485 mrad) across the field-of-view.

As AMLCD technology is at the very beginning of its use in operational applications, rapid improvements in design options are anticipated. Variations and improvements on the baseline may be made when both device R&D and manufacturing technology are completed. Other semiconductor materials under development include p-Si, x-Si, and CdSe. The substrate might be quartz or LEXAN polycarbonate plastic. Drivers may be upgraded to chip-on-glass technology or integrated on the periphery of the display substrate. Drivers will be upgraded to 64, 128, and 256 graylevels. Backlight systems will be re-invented in a variety of innovative ways to provide ten times the lumens/watt presently available in a production unit. Dimming circuitry will become 40000:1 to handle the full luminance range of 1200 to 0.03 cd m^{-2} at 50:1

contrast ratio. Horizontal pixel densities need to be doubled in direct view displays to accommodate autostereoscopic 3D without losing resolution. Pixel shape and greyscale may become less important as resolution increases.

Manufacturing technology for AMLCDs and other flat panel technologies are immature relative to other display technologies such as CRTs and electromechanical. Because of this fact one must be careful not to demand more than a manufacturer can deliver in the way of specifications. Displays for users operating in the most demanding environments, such as military, will still require more features and cost more than the least demanding, such as a climate controlled office. With that said, manufacturers should not be required to operate a manufacturing facility to more than standard commercial practice. Manufacturing technology improvements for a commercial product line can then be immediately transferred to a military product line (spin-on)--they are ideally the same line except for additional manufacturing steps and differing materials.

Current, commercial AMLCD manufacturing technology is geared to rigid manufacturing in large volume (millions) of a single design. The need is for flexible, agile manufacturing in small quantities (hundreds) of each design. This three-order-of-magnitude difference implies a completely different philosophy of plant design, and hence, that a significantly different infrastructure (manufacturing technology) must be developed for niche markets such as the military.

SPECIFICATIONS

A comparison of selected specifications for flat panel displays for commercial and military applications is provided in Table I. These applications are office laptop computer, automotive instrument panel, commercial & general aviation aircraft cockpits, military field laptop computers, and military aircraft cockpits. The entries in Table I are representative of the application type and do not pertain to any particular product or system. These and other specifications have driven designers for all these applications to select the same technology: active matrix liquid crystal display (AMLCD). Some particulars are named or stated explicitly in detail below. Space limitations permit only selected specifications to be discussed here.

Availability is an issue. Because the AMLCD has been declared a critical technology to US defense a domestic capacity must be available for a substantial portion of the

Table I. Comparison of anticipated specifications for commercial and military applications for flat panel displays.

Parameter	Office Notebook	Automotive Instrument Panel	Commercial Aircraft Cockpit	Military Field Notebook	Military Aircraft Cockpit
Critical technology					
Domestic vendor required	N	N	N	Y	Y
Foreign vendor allowed	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Design control by customer					
High volume vendor	Y	Y	Y	N	N
Low volume vendor	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Brightness, cd m⁻² (fL)					
maximum [CR]	70 (20)	150 (44) [1.5:1]	750 (220)	1200 (350)	1200 (350) [50:1]
minimum	7 (2)	0.5 (0.15)	3.4 (1)	0.03 (0.01)	0.03 (0.01)
Video (full color and monochrome)					
Frequency, Hz	24	48	48	48	84
Grayshades / primary	2-16	4-64	4-64	8-128	16-128
Viewing range (H°, V°)	40, 30	60, 60	120, 30	120, 120	30-120, 30-60
Altitude, m (ft)					
Storage/Shipping	4572 (15000)	4572 (15000)	15400 (50000)	15400 (50000)	30800 (100000)
Operational	3048 (10000)	3048 (10000)	15400 (50000)	3048 (10000)	30800 (100000)
Temperature, °C					
Storage	-25 to 60	-40 to 90	-40 to 60	-55 to 90	-55 to 90
Operational	10 to 40	-30 to 85	-30 to 60	-40 to 60	-40 to 85
Startup transient	up to 60	up to 175	up to 60	up to 175	up to 175
Times					
Storage-to-operation, m	20	1	20	20	1
MTBF, h	300	20000	30000	20000	20000
Lifetime, y	3	10	20	20	20
Acceleration, g					
Constant (RMS)	1	1	5	1	15
Shock (impulse)	1	2	15	30	30
Adverse condition operation					
Relative Humidity, %	20-80 non-condensing	0-100 condensing	0-100 condensing	0-100 condensing	0-100 condensing
Salt spray	N	N	N	Y	Y
Blowing fine sand	N	N	N	Y	Y
Immersion in mud,water	N	N	N	Y	Y
Bullet hole in inst.panel	N	N	N	Y	Y
Filters					
IR cut-off filter	N	N	N	Y (with NVS)	Y (ground attack)
EM interference	N	Y	Y	Y	Y
HUD compatible	N	Y	Y	N	Y
AR & UV coatings	N	Y	Y	Y	Y

DOD demand. Domestic means the vendor is located in the United States or Canada; ownership is irrelevant to this definition. Because display technologies (including AMLCDs in particular) are inherently dual use (the visual human-information interface), one may also consider them critical to economic security. Yet, international programs may legally be considered provided product meets mil-spec and provided that viable domestic capacity has been established.

The DOD must be able to exercise control over the design of displays in military cockpits and other military applications for the lifetime of the weapon system (some 20-50 years). Vendors must make changes upon request of design centers and depots. Vendors must not make changes DOD does not request. High volume AMLCD commercial manufacturers have proven in a number of specific instances that they will not accommodate design control for customers in niche markets like military. In a business sense, they are fighting one another during the mid-1990s for market share for flat panel TVs, laptop computers, automotive cockpits, and communications products. Such products involve several high volume \$500M production lines for each individual design--a 10.4" color VGA notebook computer screen, for example--with design changes every 18 months. Such high volume flat panel vendors are a match for high volume OEMs, like Apple, AT&T, GM, and IBM, regarding design control. Military cockpits, meanwhile need a flexible pilot manufacturing capacity to produce 10s, 100s, or 1000s of a particular design at affordable prices. By their very nature such facilities can produce a few more of a particular design at such future time as needed. The small scale production size of such a flexible manufacturer would make it a business match for niche markets like military, and able to give design control to the small volume customers in the DOD.

The sunlight readability requirements breaks into two broad classes: sun in the eye and sun on the display.

The time necessary for a person with eyes focused at infinity to look down into a display, perceive the information presented, and look back out at the world has been studied as a function of display brightness. In ambient room lighting there is a knee in the eye accommodation time at a white field luminance about 750 cd m^{-2} (220 fL) for video applications so that 8 green monochromatic grayshades can be discerned. Above this luminance the performance improvement is markedly less, as shown in Figure 2.

The F-22 program originally requested 1200 cd m^{-2} (350

Figure 2. Accommodation time as a function of luminance measured in ambient room illumination.

fL) but backed off to 700 cd m^{-2} (200 fL) [1b]. The C-130 Reliability and Maintainability Technology Insertion Program (RAMTIP) obtained 550 cd m^{-2} (160 fL) from five Hosiden a-Si AMLCDs and found this amount to be insufficient. The C-130 RAMTIP aircraft flew over 1000 flight hours, including a substantial portion under operational conditions in all climates. The U.S. military transport community believes that 700-750 cd m^{-2} (200-220 fL) is absolutely necessary. The consensus is that *at least* 700 cd m^{-2} (200 fL) is required. Optical Imaging Systems in Troy Michigan will meet this requirement on a variety of programs, including the F-22 EMD and the C-141 avionics retrofit. Science Applications International Corporation will meet this requirement on the PRAM project for F-15 ANMI. Hughes has demonstrated an ability to exceed this requirement with its HiBright™ AMLCD projection design for flight instruments designated as CRT-instrument replacements and for large area, high definition cockpit displays.

Several companies have improved the backlight scheme so as to achieve 1400-5800 cd m^{-2} (400-1700 fL) from AMLCD displays at the same power now used to obtain 550-700 cd m^{-2} (160-200 fL) from current, fluorescent tube-based designs. The issue now is how much is too much. The excess capability of the technology can then be taken in a reduction in the power required, which in turn reduces the heat dissipation problem.

Studies are now underway to obtain hard data for upper limit to the luminance required in the situation where the ambient illumination is a sun lamp shining directly into the eyes of the test-subjects [6]. The results are pertinent to the situation of the sun shining in the operator's eyes, such as a pilot flying toward a sunset or a field commander riding into a sunrise.

Dual use applications are emerging with environmental operational requirements similar to military cockpits. Ruggedized applications such as automotive are finding that their requirements should be and/or standard with Allied countries. Institutions that more ruggedized than they previously had thought. The interior of a car sitting on the desert gets as hot as that of a bubble canopy aircraft--both must survive such hot storage and work as soon as a human can sit in the cockpit. Fighter cockpit temperatures experienced during Desert Storm were up to 90 °C. Startup transient temperatures might go as high as 175 °C. Similarly, cars in arctic regions get as cold as aircraft: military specifications call for -55 °C storage and -40 °C for operation, whereas automotive, -40 °C for storage and -30 °C for operation without heaters. By contrast, commercial AMLCDs are presently specified -25 to 60 °C for storage and 10 to 40 °C for operation.

STANDARDS

Standards are now being developed for AMLCD digital flight instruments. Sizes worthy of consideration for a DOD standard product list include those listed in Table II.

One need not look beyond sizes and pixel definitions to realize the need and the potential for standard products. These candidates are representative of the variety of AMLCD flight instruments developed, or in development, since 1988. None of these is a standard item in any aircraft system; but some of them soon will be. Thus, engineers working different aircraft programs throughout DOD need to come together rapidly while the opportunity for common, standard sizes is still wide open.

CONCLUSIONS

There is a need for a documentation of requirements and, especially, a common performance specification for FPCDs and a standard for AMLCDs for military applications, beginning with cockpit flight instruments. The FPCD specification is to be separate from but does not replace the individual product specifications issued for a particular instrument by a system center, logistic center, depot, or vendor. The specification and standard are for the manufacturer of AMLCDs for display heads for all products and, thus, cuts across all systems and applications. Privity often prevents the end customer, i.e. the U.S. Government, from interfering in the relationship between an AMLCD "glass" maker and a flight instrument integrator in a contractual food chain. This FPCD specification and AMLCD standard will provide government guidance to all such relationships. There is also the possibility of a common military specification

Table II. Candidates for AMLCD FPCD standard.

Size (HxV, mm)	(D, in)	Subpix.	Density (HxV,mm ⁻¹)	
			Mono	Color
356 x 279	17.8	Qsq8b	7 x 7	4 x 4, full
305 x 171	13.5	Td-1b	12 x 12	6 x 6, full
198 x 198	11.0	Qsq4b	6 x 6	3 x 3, full
152 x 203	10.0	Qsq8b	6 x 6	3 x 3, full
203 x 152	10.0	Qvs8b	12 x 3	3 x 3, multi
159 x 159	8.8	Qsq4b	6 x 6	3 x 3, full
102 x 203	5.7	Qvs8b	12 x 3	3 x 3, multi
102 x 102	5.6	Qsq3b	5 x 5	multi
102 x 102	5.6	Qsq3b	4.7x4.7	multi
99 x 74	4.9	Qsq4b	6 x 6	3 x 3, full
86 x 73	4.5	Td-4b	6 x 6	3 x 3, full

In Table II the subpixel designator is **Aaa#b**, where
A -- number of subpixels per color pixel, Q=4, T=3),
aa -- subpixel shape (sq=square,d=dot, vs=vertical stripe)
#b -- number of bits of greyscale response of subpixel

and/or standard with Allied countries. Institutions that have not thus far been part of the process of developing these requirement, specification, and standard documents can request inclusion from the author. This process is just getting underway and will lead to documents that are beneficial to both government and industry.

Several anticipated specifications are compared across applications in Table I. Several candidate sizes for inclusion in an AMLCD standard are included in Table II. The consumer electronics mass market customer will not pay for many features or sizes that are absolutely necessary to the military customer. Hence, features vital to military aircraft flight instruments and other military applications, such as a front-line field notebook computer, will not be found in AMLCDs coming off of any high volume commercial line. Similarly for most of the sizes. Its purely a matter of business. Thus, the government must bear the cost of some militarized production since it is the most demanding customer. On the other hand, the most demanding applications typically force the creation of solutions in the form of new technologies which in turn create new industries and jobs. It with this challenge in mind that some of the stiffer anticipated specification values are set for military cockpit displays in Table I and standards in Table II. In the actual FPCD specification and AMLCD standard to be published next year it will be important to give needed performance metrics as goals in such regards as they are beyond 1994 manufacturing technology.

6. REFERENCES

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6. Sun-in-eye viewability study has been undertaken by the Naval Air Warfare Center (April 1993). For information contact Mr. James M. Moore, NAWC-AD, Code 6022, Warminster PA 18974-0591, USA.